

ON THE EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION OF THE WAVE PROPAGATION MODELLING FOR TWO-DIMENSIONAL PERIODIC TEXTILE COMPOSITES

V. Thierry^{1*}, O. Mesnil², and D. Chronopoulos¹

¹ Composites Research Group & Institute for Aerospace Technology, University of Nottingham, Nottingham, UK ² NDT department, CEA-List, Saclay, France

* Corresponding author (Victor.Thierry@nottingham.ac.uk)

Keywords: *Textile composite structures - Periodic Structure Theory - Component Mode Synthesis - Multiscale modelling – Dispersion relations*

ABSTRACT

In this article, an attempt is made toward the experimental validation of a numerical method allowing vibroacoustic and ultrasonic wave propagation analysis of complex woven composites. For this purpose, plates with a complex woven architecture were manufactured using Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) process. These composites are periodic structures composed of unit cells repeated in two directions which can be modelled realistically at a mesoscopic scale, using information from micrographic cross-sections and the mechanical properties given by the manufacturers. The numerical method combining the mode-based Component Mode Synthesis (CMS) and the Wave Finite Element (WFEM) methods allows for computing the dispersion relations of the modelled samples. Experimentally, the dispersion relations are extracted from the samples by the mean of B-scan. These experimental results are compared with the numerical results. It is shown that this methodology has a good accuracy for determining the dispersion relations of complex woven composites. It is efficient time wise and provides more information on the dispersion relations than experimental testing.

1 INTRODUCTION

Textile composites are increasingly used in modern industry due to their excellent mechanical properties [1] and especially for aerospace applications thanks to a low weight. These composite structures considered as an infinite assembly of identical elements called unit cells. The wide application of these periodic structures have attracted a lot of research for more than a decade [[2], [3], [4], [5], [6]].

3D woven composites in particular are getting more and more interest over 2D laminates as they provide higher resistance in out-of-plane loading while 2D laminates are easily subjected to delamination.

Textile composites are prone to many modes of failures such as fiber breakages, cracks and delamination. In the process of Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) - which consists of performing Non Destructive Evaluation (NDE) [7] - the earliest possible detection of damage is important.

At present, approximately 27% of an average aircraft's life cycle cost is spent on maintenance [8]. To avoid that, a technique finding increasing popularity for 'on-line' inspection is ultrasound guided waves spectroscopy [9]. As guided wave propagation in thin plates is dispersive, the velocity of wave propagation depends on the frequency and the dispersion relations need to be known.

These guided waves techniques are very efficient in traditional isotropic or even orthotropic materials as their wave propagation characteristics have been thoroughly investigated. However in strongly anisotropic composites, such as woven composites for example, these properties are not straightforward to obtain.

This paper proposes and experimentally validates a methodology for obtaining these dispersion relations for 3D woven composites.

2 SAMPLES MANUFACTURING

Three 3D woven fabrics of different architecture were used [10] to manufacture plate samples by

RTM (see Fig.1). This process was chosen because it allows to have smooth surfaces on both side of the plate which is extremely important for the experimental measurements using a laser Doppler vibrometer and also makes the geometric modelling task easier.

The woven reinforcement of the first composite has an angle interlock weave architecture and the plate measures 250 x 250 x 2 mm. The woven reinforcement of the second composite has an unconventional angle interlock weave architecture and the plate measures 250 x 250 x 2 mm. The third reinforcement is an orthogonal weave and the plate made of this material measures 250 x 250 x 5 mm.

The fabrics are made of carbon fibers while the matrix is made of resin epoxy.

Figure 1: Resin transfer moulding of the plates.

3 EXPERIMENTAL DETERMINATION OF THE DISPERSION CURVES

Piezoelectrics transducer are used to transmit a broadband signal to the plates. The input excitation signal is sinusoidal periodic (see Fig.2). Two cycles only of the sinusoidal function are modulated by a Hanning window function. The interest in having a wide frequency band in the excitation signal, is to obtain the dispersion characteristics for a wide frequency band as well.

Figure 2: Example of an input signal (—) created using a 2-cycles sinusoidal function with a central frequency of 300 kHz (- -), modulated by a Hanning window (- o -).

B-scans are performed on the plates in different direction of propagations. Displacement in the axis normal to the plates are measured in different positions on a straight line thanks to the laser Doppler

vibrometer. The displacement magnitude can be displayed as a function of space and time as shown in Fig.3.

Figure 3: U1 displacement magnitude captured numerically as a function of space x and time t in an orthotropic beam in the x -direction of propagation.

Performing a two-dimensional fast Fourier transform (2D FFT) on the acquired data allows for obtaining the dispersion curves [11]. Using the 2D FFT allows to observe several distinct modes in the frequency-wavenumber domain with input data in the space-temporal domain as displayed in Fig.4.

Figure 4: Dispersion relations of an orthotropic beam in the x -direction of propagation obtained by 2D FFT.

4 WAVE PROPAGATION MODELLING IN A TEXTILE COMPOSITE

In this part we will focus on the numerical modelling of the unconventional angle interlock woven composite. The mechanical properties of the fibers and matrix are provided by the supplier as displayed in Tab.1.

Sample	Supplier	Product reference	Filament count	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Density (g/cm ³)
<i>Warp tows</i>	Tairylyan	TC35-12K	4 x 12K	246	1.801
<i>Weft tows</i>	Tairylyan	TC35-12K	12K	246	1.801
<i>Warp interwoven tows</i>	Tairylyan	TC33-6K	6K	230	1.798
<i>Binder tows</i>	Tairylyan	TC33-6K	6K	230	1.798
<i>Resin Epoxy</i>	Gurit	Prime 20LV	-	3.35	1.10

Table 1: Mechanical properties from the datasheets provided by the fibers manufacturers and resin providers for the components of the unconventional angle interlock woven composite.

An hexagonal arrangement of the fiber is assumed to calculate the mechanical properties of the yarn. The modelling of the textile is performed with TexGen which is a software developed by the Composites Research Group at the University of Nottingham [12]. The geometric modeling is compared to micrographic cross sections of the actual composite (see Fig.5)

Figure 5: Top: Top view: photography of the composite [10] and the geometrical TexGen model are compared - Bottom: Cross sections: micrographic scans of the composite [10] and the geometrical TexGen model are compared.

The mesoscale model can then be discretized using a finite element commercial software such as Abaqus for instance in order to obtain the stiffness and mass matrices.

The dispersion curves are then calculated using the geometric model and the methodology presented in [13] that combines the WFEM and the CMS methods.

5 RESULTS

In Fig.6 is displayed the comparison of results obtained from two different numerical methods (including the one presented in Sec.4) and the experimental results (see Sec.3). A good agreement is observed.

Figure 6: Comparison of experimental and numerical results – in the background are the experimentally determined dispersion relations – ‘+’ the numerical dispersion relations obtained by fully describing the mesoscale properties of the composite [13] – ‘o’ the numerical dispersion relations using a macroscale description of the composite. All computed for different scales of the same textile composite presented in Sec.4.

Experimentally, two modes can be observed (A0 and S0). These two modes are very well predicted using the methodology we want to validate while it is poorly described by the conventional method. This has been verified for five directions of propagation for each of the three composites with different architecture.

6 CONCLUSIONS

It is shown in this paper how the numerical method presented in [13] for computing the dispersion relations in a complex woven composite has been experimentally validated.

The computation times while costly are still feasible as it takes approximately 48 hours to compute the dispersion characteristics on eight nodes possessing at least 60 Go of RAM. It should be noted that even though the macroscale model is much faster to compute, the geometrical modelling step has to be realized for both models and it takes some time to complete as well. However in both cases again, once the costly calculation is done, the dispersion relations and their mode shapes are obtained for any direction of propagation.

The macroscale model, which uses homogenized orthotropic properties, is shown to be inaccurate in its predictions of the dispersion relations, while the mesoscale model provides accurate predictions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

- This work is funded by the INNOVATIVE doctoral programme. The INNOVATIVE programme is partially funded by the Marie Curie Initial Training Networks (ITN) action (project number 665468) and partially by the Institute for Aerospace Technology (IAT) at the University of

Nottingham.

- We are grateful for access to the University of Nottingham's Augusta HPC service.
- Special thanks go to the Composites Research Group members and especially to Louise Brown who gave us advices on TexGen, to Andreas Endruweit who gracefully provided us the dry fabrics and to the lab technicians Paul and Harry who helped us manufacture the composite samples.
- These experiments were conducted at the CEA List in France and we want to thank them for the help and opportunity provided on these.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Soutis, "Fibre reinforced composites in aircraft construction," *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 143–151, 2005.
- [2] S. Mead, D. J.; Parthan, "Free wave propagation in two-dimensional periodic plates," *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 1979.
- [3] D. . J. Mead, "Wave propagation in continuous periodic structures: research contributions from southampton, 1964-1995," *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 1996.
- [4] L. Hinke, B. R. Mace, and M. J. Brennan, "Finite element analysis of waveguides," *Institute of Sound and Vibration Research*, 2004.
- [5] C. Barbarosic and M. M. Neves, "Periodic structures for frequency filtering: analysis and optimization," *Computers & Structures*, vol. 82, no. 17-19, pp. 1399–1403, 2004.
- [6] C. Droz, C. Zhou, M. N. Ichchou, and J. P. Lain, "A hybrid wave-mode formulation for the vibro-acoustic analysis of 2d periodic structures," *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, vol. 363, pp. 285–302, 2016.
- [7] S. H. S. Gopalakrishnan, M. Ruzzene, *Computational Techniques for Structural Health Monitoring*. Springer, 2011.
- [8] S. S. K. S. M. S. C. Soutis, "Damage detection in composite materials using lamb wave methods," *Institute of Physics Publishing*, 2002.
- [9] V. Giurgiutiu, *Structural Health Monitoring of Aerospace Composites*. Academic Press, 2015.
- [10] A. Endruweit and A. C. Long, "Analysis of compressibility and permeability of selected 3d woven reinforcements," *Journal of Composite Materials*, vol. 44, no. 24, pp. 2833–2862, 2010.
- [11] D. Alleyne and P. Cawley, "A two-dimensional fourier transform method for the measurement of propagating multimode signals," *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 89, no. 3, pp. 1159–1168, 1991.
- [12] H. Lin, L. P. Brown, and A. C. Long, "Modelling and simulating textile structures using texgen," *Advanced Materials Research*, vol. 331, pp. 44–47, 2011.
- [13] V. Thierry, L. Brown, and D. Chronopoulos, "Multi-scale wave propagation modelling for two-dimensional periodic textile composites," *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 2018.